

MEDICAL SCIENCES

TREATMENT OF NEOVASCULAR AGE-RELATED MACULAR DEGENERATION: A RETROSPECTIVE REAL-LIFE STUDY IN BULGARIA

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Anti-vascular endothelial growth factor (anti-VEGF) agents, such as intravitreal aflibercept, are available for the treatment of neovascular age-related macular degeneration. This manuscript aims to create a demographic profile of patients in Bulgaria and to compare the efficacy between frequent (according to label) and non-frequent (not according to label) application of intravitreal aflibercept (IVT-AFL).

Materials and methods: This is a retrospective, non-interventional, real-life study with two-year follow-up. Regular injection intervals are considered initial dosing of 3 monthly injections of 2 mg IVT-AFL followed by 2 mg IVT-AFL every 2 months for the first year. The patients who adhered to these intervals were assigned to the regular treatment group.

Results: 312 patients diagnosed with AMD were enrolled in Aflibercept treatment. The mean age was 74.2 ± 8.4 years and 60.9% were females. Of these, 49% (153 patients) were newly registered (treatment-naive), and 159 patients had started therapy at the time of study entry. The patients were divided into two groups - regular (21.8%) and irregular (78.2%). The mean visual acuity at the end of the study improved by 0.09 compared to the beginning (0.38 vs 0.29, $p < 0.05$). Visual acuity at the end of the study is significantly different between frequent and non-frequent patients (0.44 vs 0.36, $p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Irregular treatment and discontinuation of treatment by patients are common. Regular IVT-AFL treatment resulted in better VA outcomes than irregular treatment after 24 months. However, only a small proportion of patients received regular treatment over this period.

Keywords: macular degeneration, intravitreal aflibercept, real-life study, Bulgaria, regular treatment, adherence.

Introduction

Anti-vascular endothelial growth factor (anti-VEGF) agents, such as intravitreal aflibercept, are available for the treatment of neovascular age-related macular degeneration (AMD), and the goal of disease management beyond the first year is to maintain or improve functional and anatomical gains while minimizing the burden on patients of clinic visits and injections [1]. Although rapid visual and anatomic improvements could be achieved in the first year of anti-VEGF treatment, regression to baseline after initial gains is not uncommon [1]. Findings from the VEGF Trap-Eye Investigation of Efficacy and Safety in Wet AMD (VIEW) studies showed that, in the second year of treatment, the dosing interval for aflibercept could be adjusted according to the patient's response to treatment, without clinically meaningful loss of visual gains [2,3].

This manuscript aims to create a demographic profile of patients with neovascular age-related macular

degeneration in Bulgaria and to compare the efficacy between frequent and non-frequent application of intravitreal aflibercept (IVT-AFL).

Materials and methods

We conducted a retrospective, non-interventional, real-life study. The period of therapy initiation (patient recruitment) was two years, followed by two years of follow-up of all patients. Using Danny Platform software, the results of all data and ophthalmic examinations available in the hospital system were systematized and are readily available for statistical processing.

The patients were enrolled between 01.01.2019 - 31.12.2020. According to the European Summary of Product Characteristics (SPC), treatment at regular injection intervals is considered initial dosing of 3 monthly injections of 2 mg IVT-AFL followed by 2 mg IVT-AFL every 2 months for the first year. For the study and comparison with similar studies conducted, we allowed an interval of ± 2 weeks for the first year

and ± 4 weeks for the second year of treatment. The patients who adhered to these intervals were assigned to the regular treatment group. The primary endpoint was visual acuity during the follow-up.

Results

312 patients diagnosed with AMD were enrolled in Aflibercept treatment. The mean age was 74.2 ± 8.4 years and 60.9% were females. Of these, 49% (153 patients) were newly registered (treatment-naïve), and 159 patients had started therapy at the time of study entry (treated group) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Treatment-naïve (blue) vs treated patients (green) according to examined eye

The patients were divided into two groups – frequent (21.8%) and non-frequent (78.2%, Fig. 2). The mean number of the administered 2-year injections is given in Fig. 3. The mean time interval between injections for the study period in new and old patients was significantly different (2.22 vs. 4.18 months). The

mean visual acuity at the end of the study improved by 0.09 compared to the beginning (0.38 vs 0.29, $p < 0.05$) and at the end of the study is significantly different between frequent and non-frequent patients (0.44 vs 0.36, $p < 0.05$) (Fig. 4).

Fig. 2. Frequent (blue) vs non-frequent patients (green) according to examined eye

Fig. 3. Mean number of the administered 2-year injections in frequent (blue) vs non-frequent patients (green) according to the treatment status

Fig. 4. Visual acuity in the beginning (Left) and at the end of the study (Right) for regular and irregular patients.

Additionally, the mean central retinal thickness decreases by $-111.6 (\pm 115.7) \mu\text{m}$ in 3 months, $-110.8 (\pm 124.9) \mu\text{m}$ in 12 months, and $-121.4 (\pm 133.3) \mu\text{m}$ in 24 months (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Mean central retinal thickness during the follow-up.

Discussion

This manuscript describes the demographic profile of patients with neovascular age-related macular degeneration in Bulgaria and compares the efficacy between frequent and non-frequent application of IVT-AFL. The mean age and gender proportions are similar compared to other studies like RAINBOW (mean age 79.6 years, 61.3% females) and PERSEUS (mean age 77.6 years, 62.0% females) [4,5].

In terms of administration of the injections this study finds a lower number of applications in two years both for frequent (11.1 applications) and non-frequent (3.9) patients compared to other studies like PERSEUS (13.1 in frequent, 7 non-frequent) and RAINBOW (8-13 in regular, 5-12 in non-regular) [4,5]. Other real-life studies also reported high rates of both non-persistence and non-adherence [6,7,8].

This study confirms the benefits of frequent treatment in visual acuity. In PERSEUS, treatment-naïve patients improved by 8.1 letters with frequent treatment over 24 months but only by 3.1 letters with frequent treatment [5]. The proportion of treatment-naïve patients achieving a VA improvement of ≥ 15 letters was similar between frequent and non-frequent

treated cohorts [5]. In Switzerland, a real-life treat-and-extend regimen resulted in comparable anatomic and functional outcomes as were observed in the prospective registration trials of aflibercept for nAMD treatment [9]. The mean change in best corrected visual acuity was $+8.4 (\pm 14.4)$ letters at month 12 ($n = 139$) and $+5.0 (\pm 11.4)$ letters at month 24 ($n = 95$).

The high prevalence of non-frequent treatment in real-world settings is worrying since AMD is a progressive disease and loss of visual acuity is often irreversible. In this line, most patients require lifelong therapy. Thus, patient management in AMD treatment must focus more on maintaining the patient's adherence and persistence [10] and education about the disease and its complications is mandatory.

Conclusion

The study reveals that in our clinical practice non-frequent treatment and discontinuation of treatment by patients are common. Frequent IVT-AFL treatment resulted in better VA outcomes than non-frequent treatment after 24 months. However, only a small proportion of patients received frequent treatment over this period.

References

1. Patel PJ, Devonport H, Sivaprasad S, Ross AH, Walters G, Gale RP, Lotery AJ, Mahmood S, Talks JS, Napier J. Aflibercept treatment for neovascular AMD beyond the first year: consensus recommendations by a UK expert roundtable panel, 2017 update. *Clin Ophthalmol*. 2017;11:1957–66.
2. Schmidt-Erfurth U, Kaiser PK, Korobelnik JF, Brown DM, Chong V, Nguyen QD, Ho AC, Ogura Y, Simader C, Jaffe GJ, et al. Intravitreal aflibercept injection for neovascular age-related macular degeneration: ninety-six-week results of the VIEW studies. *Ophthalmology*. 2014;121(1):193–201.
3. Bayer: Eylea (aflibercept) Summary of Product Characteristics. Available at: https://www.ema.europa.eu/documents/product-information/eylea-eparproduct-information_en.pdf August 2018.
4. Weber M, Dominguez M, Coscas F, Faure C, Baillif S, Kodjikian L, Cohen SY. Impact of intravitreal aflibercept dosing regimens in treatment-naïve patients with neovascular age-related macular degeneration: 2-year results of RAINBOW. *BMC Ophthalmol* 2020;20(1):206.
5. Eter N, Hasanbasic Z, Keramas G, Rech C, Sachs H, Schilling H, Wachtlin J, Wiedemann P, Framme C; PERSEUS Study Group. PERSEUS 24-month analysis: a prospective non-interventional study to assess the effectiveness of intravitreal aflibercept in routine clinical practice in Germany in patients with neovascular age-related macular degeneration. *Graefes Arch Clin Exp Ophthalmol* 2021;259(8):2213–2223.
6. Ehlken C, Helms M, Bohringer D, Agostini HT, Stahl A. Association of treatment adherence with real-life VA outcomes in AMD, DME, and BRVO patients. *Clin Ophthalmol* 2018;12:13–20.
7. Ehlken C, Wilke T, Bauer-Steinhausen U, Agostini HT, Hasanbasic Z, Muller S. Treatment of neovascular age-related macular degeneration patients with vascular endothelial growth factor inhibitors in everyday practice: identification of health care constraints in Germany—the PONS study. *Retina* 2018;38:1134–44.
8. Gunnemann F, Vögeler J, Schmitz-Valckenberg S, Spital G, Liakopoulos S, Ziemssen F (2017) Influence of OCT examination during ranibizumab treatment of AMD patients in a real-life setting (OCEAN study). Abstract presented at the Annual Meeting of The Association for Research and Vision in Ophthalmology (ARVO), Baltimore Convention Center, Baltimore, MD, 6–11 May 2017.
9. Ebnetter A, Michels S, Prunte C, Imesch P, Eilenberger F, Oesch S, Thomet-Hunziker IP, Hatz K. Two-year outcomes of intravitreal aflibercept in a Swiss routine treat and extend regimen for patients with neovascular age-related macular degeneration. *Sci Rep* 2020;10(1):20256.
10. Lanzetta P, Loewenstein A, Vision Academy Steering C. Fundamental principles of an anti-VEGF treatment regimen: optimal application of intravitreal anti-vascular endothelial growth factor therapy of macular diseases. *Graefes Arch Clin Exp Ophthalmol* 2017;255:1259–73.